

Interoperability and Metadata Standards

Open Science can only succeed if data and systems can communicate with each other. Interoperability and metadata standards form the backbone of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) — enabling research data to be discoverable, understandable, and reusable across disciplines, institutions, and countries.

Why Interoperability Matters

Research data are only truly FAIR when they are interoperable. Interoperability means that data can be linked and exchanged on *technical*, *semantic*, and *organizational* levels:

The Dublin Core Metadata Schema

The “Simple Dublin Core” consists of 15 optional, repeatable, and generally free-text elements:

Title – Name of the resource.

Subject – Topics or keywords.

Description – A summary, abstract, or explanation.

Type – Nature or genre (e.g., “Text”, “Image”).

Source – Origin of the resource, if derived from something else.

Relation – Related resources (e.g., isPartOf, references).

Coverage – Spatial or temporal topic (place, period).

Resource Versions & Management

Date – A relevant date (creation, publication, etc.).

Format – File format or physical medium (e.g., PDF, JPEG, MP4).

Identifier – Unique reference (URL, DOI, ISBN).

Creator – Person or organization responsible for the content.

Publisher – Entity that makes it available.

Contributor – Others who helped create it.

Rights – Copyright or usage details.

Language – Language of the content (ISO language codes).

Metadata Standards

Metadata describe *what* data are, *how* they were created, and *how* they can be used. Standards ensure that this information is structured, comparable, and machine readable.

Examples of key standards:

- Dublin Core: Basic metadata for publications and datasets.
- DataCite Schema: Focused on research data and DOIs.
- DCAT-AP / DCAT-AP Austria: For data catalogues such as data.gv.at.
- DDI (Data Documentation Initiative): For social science datasets.
- CERIF: For Current Research Information Systems (CRIS).

Practical Examples from Austria and Europe

A number of Austrian and European infrastructures already apply interoperability principles:

- **AUSSDA** – uses DataCite and DDI for social science data.
- **GAMS (University of Graz)** – employs Linked Open Data and controlled vocabularies.
- **data.gv.at** – based on DCAT-AP Austria and interoperable with EU data portals.
- **EOSC Catalogue** – connects thousands of repositories using shared standards.

Find citations and scholarly resources on Open Data and other topics in the EOSC SOA Group Library on Zotero.

